

THERMAL ANALYSIS OF TOTALLY ENCLOSED FAN COOLED (TEFC) INDUCTION MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

The transfer of energy across the air-gap of an induction machine necessitates the dissipation of heat by ohmic losses in the electric circuit and by eddy current and hysteresis losses in the magnetic circuit. The performance of the insulating materials that separate the electric and magnetic circuits is highly dependent on temperature and deteriorates rapidly as temperature increases. Due to the undesirable effects that results when the thermal limit of electrical machine is exceeded, induction machines thermal analysis becomes a subject of interest for machine designers in their effort to improve machine reliability and optimization. This paper presents a thermal analysis of induction machine using the lumped parameter method formulated out of purely dimensional information and constant thermal coefficients. The equations governing the thermal behaviour of the machine are derived and solved using a commercially software package, MATLAB. The model performance is confirmed by experimental temperature data obtained from the test machine. The experimental measurement results presented show that the proposed thermal network model is capable of calculating the temperatures in the test machine with reasonable accuracy.

KEYWORDS: Squirrel-cage induction machine, thermal network model, heat transfer theory, modeling, MATLAB, simulation.

INTRODUCTION

The highest volumes of AC machines manufactured are of totally enclosed fan cooled (TEFC) design. With increasing material costs, there has been a tendency to reduce the frame size of these machines for a given output or to enhance the rating for a given frame size. The margin of error in thermal design of TEFC machines is often small hence there is an increased need for accurate analysis of thermal problems Rajagopal and Seetharamu (1997). Prediction of temperatures enables a designer to optimize the design and hence effect cost savings. This will also reduce prototype testing of series of machines in addition to reducing lead time for development of new machines.

Temperature rise is one of the major parameters that limit the rated power of any electric machine; any uncertainty in the prediction of temperature rise at critical points in the machine may result in over-designing which often involved using extra materials.

The performance of the insulating materials that separate the electric and magnetic circuits is highly dependent on temperature and deteriorates rapidly as temperature increases. From the foregoing, it is seen that the electric circuit, the magnetic circuit and the insulating part of the electrical machines are affected by the heating process in the machine emanating from the transfer of energy across the air gap. Consequently, the main limiting factor, among others, on how long an electrical machine can be operated continuously on load remains, the temperature of the various circuit elements that constitute the machine.

Most of the earlier researchers and designers have traditionally adopted resistance analog networks for prediction of temperatures. Rosanberry (1955) used thermal resistant networks to predict transient stalled temperatures of cast aluminum squirrel cage motors as early as 1955. Mellor, *et al* (1991) presented exhaustive study on lumped parameter thermal model for TEFC machines both under steady and transient thermal conditions. The model is sufficiently complex to identify the temperatures at most locations in the machine, including the peak temperatures in the end winding and the surface temperatures of the rotor. It is formulated out of purely dimensional information and constant thermal coefficients and therefore easily adapted to a range of frame sizes.

A transient thermal analysis of induction motors developed by Rajagopal and Seetharamu (1997) presented a two dimensional transient analysis of induction machines using the available heat transfer coefficient in literature. A generalized finite element code developed with Galerkin's weighted residual technique is used for analysis. The model is applied to one squirrel cage TEFC machine of 3.7kw and another surface cooled machine of 5.7kw. The predicted temperatures compared well with the test results.

A thermal analysis of induction motor using a weak coupled modeling was developed by Bastos, *et al* (1997). The authors used finite element method in the analysis of the thermal behaviour of the machine, with a weak coupled modeling between electrical and thermal phenomena. The demerit of this method lies on the fact that three-dimensional and time-dependent problems are generally involving both in software development and hardware implementation. Again it lack in flexibility in handling complex boundary conditions and geometry.

In this paper, a simplified thermal network model for a 4.8KW TEFC machine is developed using a step by step thermal network model strategy as proposed by Sarker *et al* (1993).

- Modeling the thermal network of the machine.
- Calculation of the thermal resistances and capacitances.
- Determination and calculation of the losses in the machine.
- Writing the system differential equations for the transient state studies.
- Computer simulation of the thermal model.
- Experimental verification on the test machine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Lumped-parameter models otherwise known as thermal Network Model, was used in the analysis. The advantage of the thermal network model [TNM] lies on the fact that the network parameters can be derived from entirely dimensional information, the thermal properties of the materials used in designing the machine and the constant heat transfer coefficients. This feature means the model can be easily adapted to a range machine sizes. The drawback of the thermal model is that the calculation of the model parameters can be complex and involving. However, once the model parameters are known, the resulting set of thermal algebraic and differential equations, which completely describe the machine steady and transient states thermal performances respectively can be computed with ease.

THERMAL NETWORK MODEL THEORY

In a thermal network model, it is assumed that all the heat generation in the component is concentrated in one point-usually referred as the node. A node connotes the mean temperature of the component. In a thermal network model as shown in figure1, each node is assigned a thermal capacitance, C_{th} , and heat flowing between nodes and represented as current source, P_G is passed through thermal resistance, R_{th} .

Figure 1: Thermal network model.

Thermal network models as applicable to electrical machines range from one dimension to three dimensional. However, a two dimensional or three dimensional thermal network models can be developed by connecting several

one-dimensional models together in the point of the mean temperature. A detailed analysis on this principle is given by Mellor *et al* (1991).

For small induction machines, the machine elements are represented by the temperature rise with the ambient air temperature taken as a thermal reference. The heat generation, P_G as in electrical machines represents the losses in the machine parts (e.g Stator, Rotor, etc). Thermal capacitance, C_{th} of an element is usually calculated from the geometry and material data of the element. It is expressed as,

$$C_{th} = \rho C_p v \quad (1)$$

Where,

v = volume of the element; ρ = Material density = mass / unit in kg/m^3

C_p = specific heat capacity of the material = joules of heat / $kg / ^\circ C = dQ/dT$

Q = Energy density in Joules / m^3 ; T = material temperature.

Thermal network model offers both steady and transient states solutions for the temperatures difference between the element and the ambient air temperature. The general transient equation network with n nodes and each linked to the others through thermal resistances, R_{ij} is expressed thus:

$$C_i \frac{d\theta_i}{dt} = P_i - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\theta_i - \theta_j}{R_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

where

$i = 1, \dots, n$

C_i = node thermal capacitance; θ_i = node temperature rise

R_{ij} = thermal resistance between adjoining nodes i, j ; P_i = heat generation at node i

LOSSES IN INDUCTION MACHINE

Consideration of losses in induction machine is important not only in the determination of the machine's efficiency but also in the heating of the machine and hence the rating or the obtainable power output without undue deterioration of the insulation. Losses in induction machine can be broadly classified into: Stator losses and Rotational losses.

Ohmic Losses

Ohmic losses are losses emanating from currents flowing through the stator and rotor windings. These losses are dependent approximately on the square of the load current. The ohmic losses of the stator and rotor are given mathematically by

$$P_{cu1} = 3R_s I_s^2 \quad (3)$$

$$P_{cu2} = 3R_r I_r^2 \quad (4)$$

Where

R_s = Stator resistance, I_s = Stator current per phase, R_r = Rotor resistance

I_r = Rotor current per phase

The stator and rotor resistance are dependent on the motor temperature. Therefore, the measured resistance at room temperature (θ_0) must be corrected to a specified temperature (θ). The correction for the resistance change with the temperature can be made by.

$$R = R_{20} \frac{K + \theta}{K + \theta_0} \quad (5)$$

where R is the corrected resistance at θ , and K is equal to 245 for Aluminum and 235 for Copper.

Iron Losses

The iron losses consist of the eddy losses and hysteresis losses. Iron Losses are dependent on the machine's flux which in turn is almost proportional to voltage. Iron losses in a Squirrel-cage machine can be broadly divided into three:

- Iron losses in the machine yoke, P_{Fe1Y} .
- Iron losses in the stator teeth, P_{Fe1T} .
- Iron losses in the rotor, P_{Fe2R} .

The hysteresis losses, according to Steinmetz law are proportional to frequency and to $B_{max}^{(1.5-2.5)}$ depending on magnetic saturation. The eddy current losses are proportional to the square of the frequency and also to the square of the maximum value of flux density.

Mechanical Losses

The mechanical losses often referred at friction and windage losses consist of brush and bearing friction, windage, and the power required circulating the air through the induction machine and ventilating system, if one is available. The total mechanical losses can be determined by carrying out the no-load test on the machine. By plotting the input power against the square of the phase voltage and then extrapolating to zero voltage, the intersection on the input power axis gives the total friction and windage losses.

Additional Losses

Additional losses in induction machines can be treated as stray losses. These losses are due to the non-uniform current distribution in the copper and the additional core losses produced in the iron by distortion of the magnetic flux by the load current. The stray load losses consist of the following components- especially when the motor is operated at high frequency Heller and Hamata (1997): ●Surface losses in the stator ●Surface losses in the rotor ● Pulsation losses in the stator teeth ●Pulsation losses in the rotor teeth ● Losses in the squirrel-cage winding ●Losses due to skewing with uninsulated cast aluminum squirrel-cage windings.

The additional losses are difficult to determine accurately. However, a considerable volume of work has been done and published on this subject and the causes of the losses and their determination are well established Christofides and Akins (1966), Rao and Buttler (1969), Chalmers and Richardson (1966). In this work, the stray load losses, which represent about 1.8% of the machine rated power as reported by IEEE (1991), are taken into consideration and added to the rotor losses.

HEAT TRANSFER THEORY

In order to calculate the thermal resistance of a thermal network, background knowledge of heat transfer is appropriate. Three modes of heat transfer are considered for the calculating of the thermal resistance: Conduction, Convection and Radiation.

CONDUCTION

The general equation governing heat conduction in rectangular coordinate system(x, y, z) is given by Ozisik, (1985):

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{K} \frac{Q}{\text{---}} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\alpha = K / \rho C_p \quad (7)$$

where, C_p = Specific heat of material, (J/(Kg.°C)); Q = heat generation rate, (W/m³)

ρ = density of material, (kg/m³); θ = temperature, (°C)

K = thermal conductivity, (W / (m. °C))

For one-dimensional analysis, which is applied in this work, the general expression for the conductive heat transfer is given by Fourier's law as:

$$q = -K \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \quad (8)$$

Where, q = heat flux, (W / m^2); x = distance, (m)

Therefore, the thermal resistance between two points becomes,

$$R_{th} = x_2 - x_1 / kA \quad (9)$$

Where A is the cross-sectional area, (m^2)

Thermal conductivity of most solid bodies varies very little with temperature. Pertinently, for a one-dimensional analysis, thermal resistance of a solid body can be taken to be constant. Table 1 shows the values of thermal conductivity of some materials used in the test machine.

Table 1: Thermal conductivities of the machine parts

Material	Part	K(W / °C - m)
Al-Si 20	Frame	161
Steel (0.5%C)	Shaft	54
Aluminum	Rotor cage	240
Carbon Steel(1.5%C)	Stator core and Rotor core	36
Copper	Stator winding	386
Unsaturated polyester	Stator winding impregnation and slot insulation	0.2
Unsaturated polyester	Stator winding impregnation and slot insulation	0.2
Air at 300K	Airgap, Ambient air	0.02624

Source: Griffith *et al* (1986)

Convection

Heat transfer as a result of convection is described by

$$Q = h_c (\theta_w - \theta_f) \quad (10)$$

where,

θ_w = the temperature of the surface; θ_f = the temp. as a distance point from the surface

θ_f = the temperature as a distance point from the surface

The coefficient of heat transfer, h_c is dependent on: The nature of flow (thermal or turbulent), the body geometry, the average temperature and physical characteristics of the fluid and the nature of the beam transfer (natural or forced)

These dependencies can be expressed as a function of dimensionless numbers:

$$h_c = f (Nu, Pr, Gr, Re) \quad (11)$$

The first term in equation (11) is the Nusselt number and is related to heat transfer coefficient by

$$Nu = \frac{h_c x}{K_f} \quad (12)$$

Where x is a characteristic length and K_f is the thermal conductivity of the fluid. The second term in equation (11) is the Prandtl number expressed as,

$$P_r = \frac{C_f \mu}{K_f} \quad (13)$$

Where, C_f = fluid specific heat, (J/Kg °C); μ = fluid dynamic viscosity, (kg/ms)
the third variable in equation (11) is the Grashof number which expresses the ratio of buoyancy to viscous forces.

$$G_r = \frac{g\beta(\theta_w - \theta_f)x^3}{v^2} \quad (14)$$

where, v = kinematic viscosity, (m²/s); g = acceleration due to gravity, (9.81m/s²)
 β = thermal expansion coefficient, (1/°C)

The last variable in equation (11) is the Reynolds number, Re given by
 $Re = \rho U_f x / \mu$ (15)
where, ρ = fluid density, (kg/m³); U_f = fluid velocity, (m/s)

In free convection, the fluid motion is sustained by the buoyancy forces while in forced convection the motion is maintained by external means such as fan, pump or rotating element. The ratio of the Grashof number to the square of the Reynolds number gives an important factor that distinguishes the mode of convection mechanism in given medium.

That is, $K_{gr} = G_r / Re^2$ (16)
if $K_{gr} \gg 1$, free convection dominates

However, in electrical machines forced convection dominates. For air-cooled electrical machines, the empirical formula for the heat-transfer coefficient is given in order

$$h_{c-free} = 6.5 + 0.05(\theta_w - \theta_f) \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) is used to estimate the heat transfer from the machine frame to ambient air for the test machine. The thermal resistance due to convection is estimated by

$$R_{th} = 1 / h_c A \quad (18)$$

Radiation

The net heat transfer by radiation between two real bodies is derived from the Stefan-Boltzmann's law and given by Ozisik, (1985) as,

$$q_r = A_1 \epsilon_1 \delta (\theta_w^4 - \theta_f^4) \quad (19)$$

where, A_1 = area of surface one; δ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant, [5.6697x10⁻⁸W/(m².K⁴)]
 ϵ_1 = emissivity of surface one, (0 ≤ ϵ ≤ 1). For Iron, ϵ = 0.96 and for Aluminum, ϵ = 0.08.

The thermal resistance to the surrounding due to radiation is given by

$$R_{th} = \frac{\theta_w - \theta_f}{A_1 \epsilon_1 \delta (\theta_w^4 - \theta_f^4)} \quad (20)$$

Figure 2: SCIM heat transfer mechanism.

TYPICAL CONSTRUCTION OF SQUIRREL-CAGE INDUCTION MACHINE

Figure 3 shows the typical construction of a Squirrel-cage induction machine.

Figure 3: Squirrel-cage Induction Machine Construction.

1 = Frame, 2 = stator iron, 3 = stator winding, 4,5 = end windings, 6 = rotor iron, 7 = rotor winding, 8,9 = end rings, 10 = ambient air, 11,12 = bearing, 13 = fan, 14 = cooling ribs, 15 = air gap, 16 = stator teeth, and 17 = shaft

MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATIONS OF THE THERMAL MODEL

Figure 4 shows the developed simplified thermal network model. In developing the thermal network model, the machine geometry is divided into basic elements and each element being identified by a node in the thermal network with its corresponding thermal capacitance and heat source Okonkwo (2009). The model consists of 4 nodes and 6 thermal resistances. It is assumed that the heat transfer from the rotor winding through the air-gap goes directly to the stator winding with negligible impact on the stator teeth. Any heat transfer due to radiation from the internal surfaces is neglected. By connecting the networks for the rotor, stator and frame together, the thermal network model for the machine is realized.

P₁=Frame and stator lamination; P₂ = Stator winding; P₃ = Rotor winding; P₄ = End cap
 Figure 4: Simplified Thermal Network Model

Table 2: Calculated thermal resistances and capacitances

Thermal capacitances	Values [J/K]	Thermal resistances	Values [K/W]
C ₁	4.58e5	R _{1a}	0.0416
C ₂	1.93e3	R ₁₂	10.75e-3
C ₃	7.66e3	R ₁₃	0.135
C ₄	10.06e2	R ₂₄	0.16022
		R ₃₄	0.0948
		R _{4b}	0.015

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATIONS

Frame and stator lamination thermocouples were inserted into small radial holes drilled to a depth which would align the thermocouples with the radial centre of the components. Two fine – gauge, Iron – constantan thermocouples, usually called Type J thermocouples were used and placed at locations accordingly in the

component parts of the machine. The machine was started unloaded at rated voltage of 415V and allowed to run for about one hour, before taken the temperature reading at internals of every three minutes until there were no noticeable increments. It is important to add that only the temperatures of the stator parts were recorded since the rotor winding was inaccessible but was part of the shaft. At this point, rated load was applied to the machine and the temperatures were similarly noted until there were no significant increments.

Table 3: Measured and predicted temperatures at run –up condition.

Model component	Predicted temperature [°C]	Measured temperature [°C]
Stator iron & frame	43.32	46.75
Stator winding	46.46	48.30
Rotor winding	43.87	-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Predicted temperatures of the various parts of the test machine are shown in figure 5

Figure 5: Predicted Temperatures of various parts

In the thermal analysis simulation graph of figure 5, the predicted temperature rise in the rotor winding is lower than that of the stator winding. This is as a result of the fact that the rotor winding (which is short-circuited aluminum bars) absorbs lesser heat than the stator winding which is made up of copper – hence resulting in high temperature rise.

The experimental measurement results presented show that the proposed thermal network model is capable of calculating the temperatures in the test machine with reasonable accuracy. The errors that exist between the measured and predicted temperatures may be probably as a result of the fact that the developed thermal model calculates the average temperatures inside the stator and rotor windings, whereas the installed thermoelements measure only the outside temperature of the stator and rotor windings. Probable error may also be due to the errors emanating from the calculation of the model's thermal resistances and capacitances which are dependent on the material properties of the machine – to which accurate information from the manufacturer on the same is highly necessary. These errors are, however, within acceptable limits for practical purposes.

CONCLUSION

This work has contributed to the field of induction machine modeling by providing the following:

1. An increased understanding of which phenomena influence the operation of induction machine in steady – state and dynamic conditions.
2. Thermal network model which presents a reliable solution in the estimation of average temperature of the machine parts, and

3. An interactive MATLAB program which effectively and efficiently stimulates the developed models and validation of the models with measured results.

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